

THE CONTENT AND TASKS OF TEACHING MOTHER TONGUE AND READING LITERACY TO PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Toshpulatova Niyoxon Shavkatjon qizi.

Teacher of Termiz State Pedagogical Institute.

Almanova Dilafruz Tojinorovna

Termiz State Pedagogical Institute

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Abstract.

In this article, the content and tasks of teaching native language and reading literacy to primary school students talked about.

Keywords: native language and reading literacy, ways and methods of developing students' written speech, increasing student activity.

Society always needs highly educated, creative, enterprising, innovative thinking, capable of making independent decisions. General education schools have serious tasks to improve the quality of teaching and education of primary school students. One of the main tasks of the school is to educate elementary school students to be well-educated, fluent, intelligent, literate and well-behaved, and to form a holistic, interdependent view of the world.

The issue of direct participation of students in ensuring human maturity in their education and upbringing is gaining urgent importance in the modernized national pedagogy. For this, it is necessary to awaken the conscious needs and inner interest of every child participating in the education and upbringing process. In terms of formation of independent work among students of the primary education system, mother tongue and reading literacy classes have a special place among all educational subjects. The spiritual maturity of the young generation largely depends on the effectiveness of the process of teaching them to work independently.

Therefore, the task of preparing today's young generation, our children for the complex life of tomorrow, is facing the teachers working in the field of education. The head of state said, "let's use all the possibilities so that the process of reforms and renewals that are being implemented today will become a common goal that mobilizes everyone living in our generous land for practical work." It also refers to internal education.

At present, great attention is being paid once again to the problem of organizing a system of tasks related to the topic in the classes of mother tongue and reading literacy for primary school students and being able to convey it correctly to the students. Teaching mother tongue in primary grades includes not only grammar, spelling and related speech development methods, but also methods of reading and writing in the classroom and outside the classroom. Based on this, the following tasks are taken into account when teaching mother tongue in primary grades:

a) defining and justifying the content, size and existing system of the native language course in primary grades, that is, the program of the course (literacy, reading, grammar, spelling, speech development, etc.);

b) to study the process of formation of knowledge and skills from reading and writing, as well as the difficulties faced by students in this process, to analyze the cause of mistakes, to develop types of work that help to prevent and correct them;

d) students' clear understanding and thorough assimilation of the educational material given in their mother tongue, the ability to apply the knowledge they have acquired in practice and the general development of students, i.e. their mind, memory, observation, memory, logical thinking, developing methods and tools that help to develop creative thinking and speech;

e) implementation of educational tasks set before schools in connection with teaching the mother tongue, formation of moral and aesthetic qualities in students. [8]

Knowledge of lexicology, vocabulary work at school (conducting various exercises on synonyms and antonyms, working on polysemous words, their meaning coloring) It is very important for proper organization.

Methodology in studying word composition and word formation, word formation, etymology, grammar serves as the basis.

The content of teaching the mother tongue in schools is adapted to the task of our state for the school at the current stage of society's development. These tasks are multifaceted, and their fulfillment is aimed at developing the minds of students, giving them ideological-political, moral, aesthetic and labor education. As a result of teaching the mother tongue, the students will be able to express their thoughts grammatically correct, stylistically clear, meaningful, following the tone and write it correctly. This task is a unique feature of the Uzbek language as a subject of study, and it is carried out in connection with general educational tasks aimed at forming the student as a person. The content of the knowledge given in the native language course is about the sound structure of the Uzbek language and the methods of phonetic expression in written speech (phonetic and graphic); about the change of words and the connection of words in a sentence (grammatical, morphological and syntactical); about the morphemic structure of the word and the methods of word formation (about word formation); lexicological about the lexical-semantic group of words); knowledge of the correct writing principles of the Uzbek language and the use of punctuation marks (orthographic and punctuation). This knowledge is manifested, firstly, in grammatical, phonetic, and word formation concepts, and secondly, in graphic, orthographic, and punctuational rules. In addition, the Uzbek language course includes phonetic, graphic, morphological, syntactic and other skills and competencies.

For learning in primary grades, knowledge was chosen that would provide a basis for conscious acquisition of the language and the formation of graphic and spelling skills in students. In the field of phonetics and graphics, students acquire knowledge that allows them to correctly understand the sound composition of a word, the characteristics of vowels and consonants, the importance of sound in a word in distinguishing its meaning, and also It is possible to consciously determine the ratio (connection) between the sound and graphic form of the word, to write the word correctly.

From the field of morphology, knowledge of great practical importance for conscious mastering of words and its correct use has been recognized. Primary school students learn word groups (nouns, adjectives, numbers, pronouns, verbs) at different levels starting from the 1st grade. From syntax to the program, the knowledge about the sentence as a speech unit, word connection in the sentence, primary and secondary clauses is included. Regarding the

morphemic structure of the word, the important signs of each morpheme, their importance and their influence on each other in the word, in the amount necessary for elementary school students to understand and use in writing words correctly. information provided.

In conclusion, it can be noted that the content of the native language of the primary class is being improved based on the many years of observations, experiences, and analysis of the results of the Methodist scientist. Special attention is paid to the practical importance of teaching the mother tongue.

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